

A Method for the Determination of Copper in Commercial Aluminium.

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Copper in commercial aluminium is usually estimated by dissolving out the aluminium by means of caustic soda or sodium carbonate solution followed by any standard volumetric or colorimetric method (Lunge, "Technical Methods of Chemical Analysis," Vol. II, Part I, p. 347). It has now been found that aluminium may be completely brought into solution by means of dilute sulphuric acid leaving behind copper which may amount to the extent of 5 per cent. in the commercial samples. The accuracy of the results obtained by the present method compares very favourably with that of the existing methods. The following table gives the data obtained by the different methods.

Sample.	Cu by H_2SO_4 method.	Cu by $NaOH$ method.	Cu by H_2S method.
Indian aluminium	0.20 %	0.22 %	0.20 %
English aluminium	1.02	1.03	1.00
Pig aluminium (tooth-ed bar.)	0.30	0.30	0.20
" " "	0.22	0.22	0.24
" " "	4.58	4.62	4.61
" " "	0.82	0.815	0.80
" " "	1.15	1.13	1.12
" " "	0.100	0.096	0.095*
" " "	0.658	0.655	0.690
Shot aluminium	0.067*	0.065*	0.068*

* colorimetrically

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental procedure is as follows:—

About 2 g. of very thin drillings or shavings of the sample are introduced into a beaker (250 c.c.) and 100 c.c. of sulphuric acid (1 part concentrated acid of density 1.84 and 5 parts water) are added. The beaker, covered by means of a clock glass, is then allowed to simmer on a hot plate or burner taking care that the volume of the solution does not get below 75 c.c. Should this happen, water may be added. When all the aluminium has gone into solution, the beaker is removed from the source of heat and the contents quickly filtered and washed thoroughly with cold water till free from acid. A small hole is then made in the apex of the filter paper and the residue washed down into a beaker. About 5 c.c. of warm concentrated nitric acid are added through the sides of the filter paper which is again washed with hot water till free from acid, care being taken that the volume does not exceed 50 c.c. The copper is then brought into solution by heating and the nitrous fumes are removed by boiling. The copper is then estimated iodometrically by Low's method after neutralisation of the acid by ammonia.

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Received July 30, 1929.